

Title

The Role of Information Science within the Clinical Translational Science Ecosystem

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Introduction

Translational science seeks to decrease the time it takes to “translate” bench research into healthcare practice in order to deliver new interventions to the communities and patient populations that need them.¹ Since 2012, the mission of the National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS) has been to use translational science principles to more quickly convert biomedical research into better health outcomes.² The National Institutes of Health (NIH) has awarded Clinical and Translational Science Awards (CTSA) since 2006, funding a network of hubs (the CTSA Program) to advance clinical and translational science (CTS) throughout the United States.

Academic health sciences libraries have long partnered with their constituents to support basic, clinical, and translational research, and the related information needs of clinicians and patient populations. Most health sciences libraries have services supporting the research lifecycle, making them natural partners in advancing CTS. Many libraries have a rich history of working with CTSA Program hubs and other translational efforts such as the IDEa Clinical & Translational Research Network (CTR-N).³

In 2023, the CTSA Program Notice of Funding Opportunity (NOFO) was revised and restructured. The new announcement consists of five elements: Overview, Strategic Management, Training & Outreach, CTS Resources and Pilots, and a CTS Research Program.⁴ This new structure represents an evolution of the CTSA Program and advancement of the science of translational science. A significant modification to the CTSA Program involves enhanced requirements for the dissemination and implementation (D&I) of translational research. The translational science spectrum illustrates how each stage of translational research informs and builds upon the next. These new requirements ensure that translational research leads to health impacts that address health disparities, ultimately benefiting the public good.⁵⁻⁷

In 2013, Holmes et al. explored the ways that libraries support CTS based on the functional areas defined by the NCATS program at that time.⁸ Like the CTSA Program, health sciences libraries have experienced a significant period of evolution over the last decade, offering an opportunity to revisit, update, and reimagine their support of translational science. This article aims to revisit potential library partnerships with Clinical Translational Science Hubs (CTSH^a) considering both the evolving structure and mission of these hubs and the expansion in library services in the past 11 years. Here we address areas of health sciences library support for each of the CTSA Program’s five functional areas contained in the NOFO. Since CTS programs, individual CTSH, and libraries are each unique in their structure and

^a Includes CTSA Program Hubs, other institution-based CTS institutes, and is also relevant for a wide range of NIH funding opportunities and other programs supporting clinical translational science.

priorities, this article is intended to serve as a jumping off point for CTSH and libraries to explore potential partnerships. Partnership with health sciences libraries can help connect researchers to relevant library services, support scholarly activities by CTSH investigators, and promote the development of new library services and infrastructure supporting CTS. The authors also believe that the principles outlined are applicable in a variety of settings beyond CTSH and can be a useful scaffold upon which to design, develop, and disseminate library programs and resources in support of biomedical research and its application to patient care and population health.

Literature Review

Support for translational science by health sciences libraries and librarians is well-represented in the biomedical literature. To conduct this literature review, the authors searched PubMed to identify library or informationist projects for CTS or clinical and translational research efforts and included articles that explicitly referenced library collaborations that had librarian co-authors working with their institutional CTSH. Additionally, the authors searched Medical Library Association (MLA) Annual Meeting abstracts for papers and posters from MLA annual meetings 2013-2023, including those that mentioned “translational science” in the abstracts.

The literature search identified articles and projects that discuss efforts at institutions with health sciences libraries that are engaged in CTSH work, both in broad terms regarding services as well as specific programs and partnerships. Library partnerships often feature development of tools and infrastructure to foster discovery and collaboration, critical components of any CTSH. Assessment of information needs⁹ and creation and maintenance of researcher profile systems¹⁰ represent examples of this role. Additionally, active engagement with pilot projects to develop and create CTS personas to understand specific CTS roles has grown over several years.¹¹⁻¹⁴ The development and use of personas contributes to an understanding of the needs of a translational science team and highlights how health science libraries can provide support.

Libraries also contribute to evaluation and assessment of research impact. Examples include use of social network analysis (SNA) tools to track and visualize inter-institutional interactions of CTSH programs and investigators¹⁵, creating a systematic review core facility to support evidence synthesis research¹⁶, and hosting library-based drop-in services for CTSH core services, therefore providing a one-stop shop for support. In 2016, librarians and program staff from numerous CTSA Program Hubs identified inconsistencies in the categorization of CTSA-linked publications, and applied machine learning to create a structure by which publications can be classified according to their phase in the translational research spectrum.¹⁷ In 2017, librarians partnered with a CTSA Hub to define the concept of “translational research”.¹⁸ Librarians have also played critical roles in defining and developing models for assessing translational science impact¹⁹⁻²³ and many health science libraries regularly contribute bibliometric, social network, and funding analyses.²⁴⁻³¹

Development of the CTS librarian workforce continues to be a critical component in the ability of libraries to meet this need on their campuses. To meet this pressing workforce development need, Cleveland, et al. developed a virtual three-credit hour graduate-level course, “Genomics and Translational Medicine for Information Professionals”³² through the Health Informatics Program at the University of North Texas College of Information. Peer learning and exchange also plays an important

role in the ongoing development of a CTS-minded library workforce. This often occurs through professional development activities and trainings at professional meetings, where librarians actively share and discuss their support of translational science through presentations, posters, and conference papers given at a range of events, most predominantly the Medical Library Association annual meeting, but also at CTS Program meetings, the Association of Clinical and Translational Sciences annual meeting, the AAMC Group on Information Resources meeting, and American Medical Informatics Association meetings. These presentations cover a wide range of topics, including library support for clinical research scholars.^{33,34}

Library Support Activities

Library support can align with key functional areas described in the CTSA Program NOFO. The section below and Table 1, describe potential service areas and can be used by CTSH and their libraries to generate ideas for collaboration and partnership.

Overview (Element A)

The Overview element requires that CTS institute applicants define the overall vision and strategic goals, and related strengths for the research environment, including descriptions of the team and their high impact achievements, and the expected impact on science and public health⁴. Many health sciences libraries provide scholarly impact services that use bibliometrics and alternative metrics to illustrate the strengths and impact of CTS by measuring the dissemination and use of scholarly outputs. Library expertise around scholarly impact can support CTSH by assessing and visualizing the connections of scholarship between partner and collaborator institutions, as well as the impact of the hub on scholarly outputs.^{30,31} These scholarly impact metrics can be used to demonstrate the value of CTS over time and can assist in the creation of evaluation metrics and references that support grant application narratives and funder reporting requirements. Librarian-led literature reviews can also strengthen application narratives.

Use Case Example

Librarians and researchers collaborated to develop CTS Personas, a portfolio of nineteen evidence-based profiles based on roles across the ecosystem of translational research, spanning basic research to public health, including two patient profiles.^{13,14} These representative profiles are designed to assist CTSH in evaluating the resource and service needs for supporting the translational science workforce and community, including development of software, tailored educational and communication materials, understanding key perspectives and needs, providing context to better support workforce development, and targeted guidance for such pressing issues as institutional considerations of the National Institutes of Health's (NIH) Data Management and Sharing Policy.³⁵

Strategic Management (Element B)

The Strategic Management element requires a description of operations and infrastructure needed to support the CTSH⁴. Activities in strategic management include defining governance, leadership

structure, integration within the CTSA Program national network, and coordination of programs. Central to the role of health sciences libraries are the requirements for ongoing assessment and program evaluation, and dissemination/implementation activities. Health sciences libraries can support strategic management by participating as a member of the CTSH's leadership/governance to oversee information-related planning and strategy, assisting with software and resource licensing, providing liaison services for research support, and acting as a liaison between libraries at partner and collaborating institutions. Health sciences libraries support dissemination by providing guidance on scholarly communication practices, compliance with federal funders' open access and data sharing mandates, and open science strategies. In addition, many health sciences libraries provide services and resources to support assessment and program evaluation, including faculty profile systems, collaboration analyses, mentorship efforts, data visualization techniques, and scholarly impact metrics.

Use Case Example

In 2023, the University of Virginia Health Sciences Library partnered with the integrated Translational Health Research Institute of Virginia (iTHRIV) to develop training and resources for researchers. This initiative aimed to support research teams in preparing for and implementing the new National Institutes of Health (NIH) Policy for Data Management and Sharing (DMSP). A dedicated website, hosted by the library and accessible through the iTHRIV Research Concierge Portal, offers policy guidance, including links to NIH-hosted information, resources from other institutions, and newly developed UVA templates and suggested proposal language.^{36,37} This collaboration between iTHRIV and the Health Sciences Library provided institutional leadership, facilitating communication and engagement with researchers by leveraging the long standing relationship between the library and iTHRIV.

Training & Outreach (Element C) - Workforce Development for Clinical Research Staff Professionals Module and Community and Stakeholder Engagement Research Module

The Training & Outreach element includes two distinct modules: 1) workforce development for clinical research staff professionals and 2) community and stakeholder engagement⁴. Training and outreach are foundational components of most health sciences library services, providing a unique opportunity for CTSH to leverage an existing, well-developed strength of health sciences librarians.

Workforce Development for Clinical Research Staff Professionals

The workforce development for clinical research staff professionals module encompasses a variety of educational activities, including workshops, seminars, online classes, and other opportunities that support professional development, with an emphasis on early career researchers and team science. Training and outreach are core functions of health sciences libraries and easily translatable to the CTS environment. Libraries can partner in the creation of CTS information guides, information discovery through databases like PubMed, training in and support for systematic reviews and evidence syntheses, data management planning, and the use of scholarly repositories. In addition, many libraries offer resources and expertise to support instruction on best practices in data sharing, data science skills such as coding, the science of team science³⁸, open science best practices, rigor and reproducibility in science,

and knowledge and expertise supporting IRB (Institutional Review Boards) and/or IACUC (Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee). In support of mentorship, librarians have developed and published code that uses structured data to automatically generate training grant tables illustrating mentor mentee relationships in NIH format.³⁹ Health science libraries are increasingly offering training in artificial intelligence (AI) as applied to information discovery tools supporting research, such as prompt engineering, ethics, copyright, and citation of use.⁴⁰

Use Case Example

The University of Pittsburgh Health Sciences Library System has actively partnered with their campus to offer training, resources, and services to CTS researchers for many years. These offerings cover a broad range of topics such as informatics and data science, scholarly publishing, compliance, research integrity, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) best practices. Recognition for librarians' teaching contributions within the CTSI Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) Center have been recognized with secondary appointments with the University's Clinical and Translational Science Institute (CTSI).

Community and Stakeholder Engagement Research

The community and stakeholder engagement research module includes support for building effective teams, dissemination of research, and diversification of representation in research teams and participants to create meaningful connections between research findings with individual communities, especially rural, minority and underserved populations. Health sciences librarians are critical partners in understanding and addressing bias in the research lifecycle and can create information guides on anti-racist practices in primary and secondary research, data, publishing, and information searching^{41,42}. Additionally, librarians have considerable expertise in teaching how to find and apply credible health information and how to adopt the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), ensuring researchers, members of the public, and community-based health organizations have access to the best information from reliable sources. Libraries can also be partners in community engagement through their relationships with public libraries and other community organizations by providing health information to consumers, as well as educating public librarians in consumer health information best practices. Librarians are skilled in the creation of online information guides, best practices in licensing resources, and support of citizen science, all of which can advance goals around community and stakeholder engagement.

CTS Resources and Pilots (Element D) - Resources and Services (R&S) Module, CTS Pilot (Pilot Module Leader), and Health Informatics (HI Module Leader).

The CTS Resources and Pilots element includes three modules: 1) resources and services, 2) clinical and translational science pilots, and 3) health informatics.⁴

Resources and Services

The resources and services module may support needs in a broad range of areas, from biostatistics and research design to informatics to research recruitment to provision of core lab equipment to general training opportunities. Many health sciences libraries have developed services to support the use of

REDCap, a data collection tool; data visualization tools; coding languages such as R and Python for data analysis and reporting; as well as other tools to support the research lifecycle.^{43,44} Libraries may provide instruction for data management, federal funder open access mandates, rigor and reproducibility, and best practices in responsible research.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ Librarians acting as data governance custodians can provide regulatory support for protected data sets inside a secure data enclave collaborating with IRBs to ensure data protection and authorized access.⁴⁸

CTS Pilots

The CTS pilot module provides support for new and innovative CTS projects. Health sciences libraries provide a variety of research support services. Libraries provide support in information seeking to ensure that CTS projects are aware of relevant scientific evidence in the scholarly record. Libraries may also provide guidance on the dissemination of information, including journal selection, data description, repository selection (including use of local institutional repositories), and the use of information management and synthesis tools. Because facilitating the research process is a core aspect of health sciences libraries, many library initiatives may be of interest for CTS pilot projects, including the development of tools for data discovery and identification of potential collaborators.

Health Informatics

The health informatics module provides resources and support for a variety of research activities, including data management and sharing, cohort discovery via i2b2, extraction of Electronic Health Record data, computable phenotyping, data description and discovery, privacy, and security. Libraries regularly provide training and consultation services and often serve as co-investigators on projects. They also can support researchers through the creation of information guides and delivery of other resources. Many libraries have developed expertise and provide training and support in metadata, federal funder open access and data sharing mandates, data ethics, best practices for reproducibility, and open science practices and tools. Libraries have invested in training or tools to support bioinformatics and data science services.^{18,49-51} Libraries are also playing important roles to meet the urgent need for training, support, and responsible use of AI tools.

Libraries are frequent and active collaborators in the development, implementation, and/or support of institutional profile systems and data to facilitate collaboration.^{52,53} This work builds upon library expertise and resources and supports a range of efforts beyond researcher profiles that support team science. They also play a central role in data sharing and discovery. Libraries have developed specialized data catalogs to facilitate discovery of existing institutionally created data sets that can be located/mined for secondary use.^{54,55} These catalogs are designed to encourage collaboration and cross-disciplinary discovery. Libraries are also involved in the development and delivery of repository infrastructures to support funders' data sharing mandates and support FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) best practices and equitable access to knowledge. Examples of this include institutional repositories^{56,57} and partnerships on repository projects with domain-specific repositories or generalist repositories, such as the NIH Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative.^{58,59}

Use Case Example

Weill Cornell Medicine librarians and administrators collaborated with the Informatics team of Weill Cornell Medicine's Clinical & Translational Science Center to develop

ReCiter^{51,60}, an open source publication management and reporting system. ReCiter identifies individual-authored publications in PubMed by harnessing institution-specific identity data. Its companion system, ReCiter Publication Manager⁵³ allows everyone at Weill Cornell to generate reports and publication lists for 20,000 faculty, students, alumni, and residents. It also empowers these end users to generate bibliometric reports for individual full-time faculty which summarize data from iCite^{52,53}, NIH's bibliometric reporting tool.

CTS Research Program (Element E)

The CTS Research Program is intended to be a discrete research project, with the intent that project innovations are generalizable in other CTS settings. The library research support services described in the preceding sections – such as literature searching, data management support, evidence synthesis, data visualization, and coding instruction – can serve to support this project through the research lifecycle. Furthermore, because the research project(s) described in Element E may have more specific needs, CTSH are encouraged to contact your library about other resources or services that may be available.

Table 1. Clinical and Translational Science Awards (CTSA) element components and descriptions aligned with library support contributions that can support local Clinical and Translational Science (CTS) work

Element A: Overview

The Overview focuses on the global vision for the research environment of a CTSH and participation as a member of the national CTSA network. This includes a description of the organization, definition of strategic priorities, strategies for evaluating the impact, and dissemination of generalizable results that are of interest to the advancement of scientific knowledge and public health.

Library support can include:

- Provide assessment and visualization of collaborative activities and interpersonal or inter-organization partnerships.
- Provide assessment and visualization of areas of strength or opportunity; participate in the identification of strengths or opportunities.
- Support demonstration of research impact through bibliometrics, scientometrics, and meaningful use of alternative metrics.
- Provide guidance and text for metrics and impact statements to include in the grant narrative, such as citations resulting from previous CTSA Program (or related) initiatives, examples of knowledge translation, open science highlights, and descriptive text about collaboration impact.

Element B: Strategic Management

Coordination of activities that govern the relationships between the participating partners and collaborators. Areas of focus include institutional contributions and resources, definition and governance, organizational leadership, integration within the CTSA network, and coordination of consortium activities.

Library support can include:

- Serve as active members of the leadership team and advise on information planning and strategy.
- Act as a liaison between libraries at partner and collaborator institutions.
- Provide consultation and guidance for information tools and resources that support reporting, assistance with collaboration, discovery, and evaluation.
- Manage faculty profile system and/or information resources used to populate these systems and associate personnel with research outputs.
- Develop/deliver publication metrics and impact assessments based on iCite or other tools.
- Provide guidance and leadership on scholarly communication and federal funding open access and data sharing mandates.
- Create visualization of author relationships, collaboration, and impact, including collaboration, mentorship, and interpersonal or inter-organization partnerships
- Provide assistance with vendor communications and licensing of software or other information resources.
- Develop and deliver library bioinformatics services and resources.
- Provide resources and support for marketing and dissemination strategies.
- Develop and partner on open science strategies and programming.

Element C: Training & Outreach - Workforce Development for Clinical Research Staff Professionals.

Focuses on training, education, and mentoring. Educational activities may include seminars, workshops, online courses, or other opportunities related to professional development and career advancement. Associated activities may focus on general workforce training, early career development, or promoting diverse representation and voices of underrepresented persons and marginalized communities.

Library support can include:

- Compile holdings and create CTS-specific guidance, including research guides, repository resources, and other relevant resource collections.
- Provide guidance and training on technical and highly specialized topics such as data science methods and biostatistics tools, assistance on the use of AI information discovery tools supporting research (including prompt engineering, ethics, etc).
- Support with information discovery, management & synthesis tools (PubMed, Covidence, Rayyan, Zotero, etc).
- Provide instruction and consultation in the use of information tools to disseminate the effectiveness of tools, methods, processes, and training paradigms, including open access/open science best practices.
- Provide training and consultation in scientific writing and scholarly publishing.
- Provide training and consultation services for systematic and scoping reviews and other evidence syntheses.
- Offer consultation and training on the use of online learning platforms.
- Provide knowledge and expertise services (e.g., instruction, consultation support, support and assist with the development of curricula) for key topics for clinical research staff, including research rigor and reproducibility, IRB and/or IACUC, team science, data management planning, open science, metadata, critical appraisal, etc.; this can be supplemented with online companion guides on these topics designed and written specifically for clinical research staff.
- Provide space for collaboration and training events for the CTS workforce.

- Provide instruction and consultation in the use of information tools to disseminate the effectiveness of tools, methods, processes, and training paradigms.

Element C: Training & Outreach - Community and Stakeholder Engagement Research Module.

Focuses on supporting research that builds effective teams, integrates community stakeholders into the research process, disseminates results to the community and stakeholders in the national network. Methods include integration recruitment and retention of underserved populations in clinical trials and clinical studies and the adoption of evidence based practices that investigate outcomes with the goal of advancing health equity.

Library support can include:

- Create resource guides for clinical professionals on best practices and resources for patient and community engagement.
- Provide instruction and consultation on evidence-based information tools and resources.
- Engage in discussions about the licensing of resources for institutional partners.
- Navigate legal opportunities for resource sharing.
- Facilitate collaboration with Community Based Health Organizations (CBHO) and other members of the community.
- Provide or partner on training and resources to support open equitable access to research from the CTS institute.
- Provide support to investigators for making data and research products accessible and discoverable to the community.
- Provide instruction for understanding and addressing bias in the research lifecycle.
- Explore and help license resources that advance learning and practice for culturally competent, community-based research.
- License/manage/provision scientific software via an institutional software hub.
- Partner on community engagement opportunities to inspire participation in research, such as through community health information activities, basic research skills, citizen science; consider collaboration with community public library partners.
- Develop and make available physical and virtual exhibits to highlight community history on health topics.

Element D: CTS Resources and Pilots - Resources and Services (R&S) Module.

Supports biostatistics, epidemiology, research design, and regulatory support (BERD). Components include informatics, clinical trials and protocol development, data collection, training, research support tools and resources.

Library support can include:

- Provide basic instruction and consultation in the use of statistical software (e.g., R, Python, SAS, SPSS) and biostatistical methodology.
- Provide instruction and consultation support for research data management.
- Support use of institutional and national repositories.
- Support best practices in data description and metadata for responsible research.
- Provide support and guidance on data governance and management of restricted data enclaves (regulatory support).
- House biostatistics seminar recordings and training materials in a collection in the institutional repository.

- Support research integrity practices.

Element D: CTS Resources and Pilots - CTS Pilot Module.

Provides moderate support for pilot projects for new and innovative research projects relevant to the advancement of CTS. Activities include the development of new research methodologies, use cases that make CTS processes more efficient, dissemination of CTS techniques, or use of existing data for secondary analysis.

Library support can include:

- Support with information discovery, management & synthesis tools (PubMed, Covidence, Rayyan, Zotero, etc).
- Provide instruction and consultation on systematic reviews and other evidence synthesis types. Libraries may also provide methodological support as members of the research team.
- Provide instruction and consultation in the use of information tools to uncover what is known in the body of scholarly literature.
- Assist with the dissemination of information including journal selection and online repositories.
- Implement and host Data Catalogs to facilitate the discovery and use of existing data for secondary analysis.
- Meet with pilot teams early in their work to provide guidance and resources that support good data practices, establish tracking of research outputs, and support dissemination strategies.

Element D: CTS Resources and Pilots - Health Informatics Module.

Provides educational and technological support for research informatics and open science. Activities may include resources and training related to data, including management, sharing, visualization, description, privacy, security, and discoverability. May also include tools, statistical methodology, evaluation, text mining, machine learning, natural language processing, and clinical decision support.

Library support can include:

- Create central resource guides on the discovery and use of data for secondary analysis.
- Collaborate to organize and manage access to data sets.
- Provide training on key data science tools.
- Partner to develop local data management and sharing policies, practices, and solutions (e.g., DMPTool).
- Support and enhance institutional repositories to share and host data sets and other research objects.
- Offer data curation services and training.
- Provide training on open science practices and tools including the FAIR principles, support and training for data ethics.
- Provide institutional guidance, consultations, and training on metadata best practices.
- Provide training and support for responsible use of AI tools.
- Provide library bioinformatics service.
- License/manage/provision scientific software via an institutional software hub.

Element E: CTS Research Program.

A discrete research project that aims to address a translational research question in a particular disease or intervention that is generalizable to other CTS projects.

Library support can include:

- Support described in Elements A – E, as well as potentially other specialized resources and services to reflect the specific needs of the projects.

Discussion

The integration of academic health sciences libraries' specialized expertise and support activities into CTS is a strategic alliance aimed at bridging gaps between research innovation and practical application. The breadth and depth of the examples above underscore the significant contributions of libraries in supporting CTS, highlighting their role in enhancing research visibility, developing a skilled and trained research workforce, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration, and increasing compliance with evolving research mandates.

Libraries have proven instrumental in leveraging bibliometric and alternative metrics to showcase the impact of CTS, including visualizing the connections of scholarship across institutions and illustrating the dissemination and utility of CTS scholarly outputs. Furthermore, librarian expertise in scholarly communication, knowledge of federal mandates regarding publishing and data management/sharing, and implementation of open science initiatives, including the FAIR principles, can contribute to a foundation for robust governance and operational structures. This involvement ensures that information-related strategies are aligned with the overarching goals of CTS, facilitating seamless integration within the CTSA Program or other translational science national network.

Libraries offer specialized knowledge that supports the professional development of early career researchers at every stage of the research lifecycle. Additionally, library proficiency in community and stakeholder engagement ensures that research findings are effectively disseminated to public health stakeholders, fostering evidence-based community interventions and enhancing public health outcomes.

The provision of specialized resources and services further exemplifies the critical role of academic health sciences libraries in CTS. By offering support for research tools such as REDCap, R, Python, SAS, and SPSS, and providing instruction in data management and compliance with open access mandates, libraries facilitate rigorous and responsible research practices. Furthermore, library expertise in evidence synthesis enables them to lead research teams in using best practices and developing research protocols that directly ensure the replicability of these evidence reviews. Moreover, their involvement in data governance and bioinformatics services underscores a commitment to maintaining high standards of research integrity and reproducibility. Libraries can act as a liaison between libraries at partner and collaborator institutions, ensuring researchers and administrators have access to their institutional resources supporting CTS.

The opportunity to consider clinical translation science in the context of the CTS offers new opportunities for health sciences libraries to collaborate with CTS and co-develop training and

resources to meet emerging needs in an efficient and effective manner. It is important to recognize that these partnerships can start and be productive even before formal funding mechanisms are in place. Engaging during the proposal development phase is a great way to raise awareness of existing library services and resources that support the translational science spectrum. This early engagement can also pave the way for deeper and long lasting partnerships between health sciences libraries and CTSH.

Ultimately, the multifaceted support provided by health sciences libraries is indispensable to the success of CTS. Their contributions across the functional areas demonstrate the translational potential of this collaboration. As CTS programs continue to evolve, the sustained inclusion of health sciences librarians will be crucial in ensuring that scientific discoveries are efficiently translated into tangible health benefits for communities.

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Works Cited

1. Vogel A. Translational Science Principles. Published online April 19, 2024. <https://ncats.nih.gov/about/about-translational-science/principles>
2. National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS). In: *NIH Almanac*. NIH; 2024. <https://www.nih.gov/about-nih/what-we-do/nih-almanac/national-center-advancing-translational-sciences-ncats>
3. IDeA Clinical and Translational Research Programs. IDeA Clinical and Translational Research Programs. Accessed July 26, 2024. <https://www.nigms.nih.gov/Research/DRCB/IDeA/Pages/idea-ctrp.aspx>
4. PAR-21-293: Clinical and Translational Science Award (UM1 Clinical Trial Optional). <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/pa-files/PAR-21-293.html>
5. Translational Science Spectrum | National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences. Accessed July 29, 2024. <https://ncats.nih.gov/about/about-translational-science/spectrum>
6. Mahoney JE, Stevens KR, Mehta T. Cross walk between consensus recommendations and new NCATS PAR-21-293 requirements for D&I in CTSA hubs. *J Clin Transl Sci*. 6(1):e17. doi:10.1017/cts.2022.4
7. Lema C, Cheng KW, Anderson DM, et al. Simultaneous submission of seven CTSA proposals: UM1, K12, R25, T32-predocutorial, T32-postdoctoral, and RC2: strategies, evaluation, and lessons learned. *J Clin Transl Sci*. 2024;8(1):e33. doi:10.1017/cts.2024.14

8. Holmes KL, Lyon JA, Johnson LM, Sarli CC, Tennant MR. Library-based clinical and translational research support. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA*. 2013;101(4):326-335. doi:10.3163/1536-5050.101.4.017
9. Reich M, Shipman JP, Narus SP, et al. Assessing clinical researchers' information needs to create responsive portals and tools: My Research Assistant (MyRA) at the University of Utah: a case study. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA*. 2013;101(1):4-11. doi:10.3163/1536-5050.101.1.002
10. Zeidler A, Rood W. Researcher profiling systems: fostering collaboration on a regional medical campus and clinical and translational science award institution. *J Med Libr Assoc*. 2023;111(4):837-838. doi:10.5195/jmla.2023.1622
11. Gonzales S, O'Keefe L, Gutzman K, et al. Personas for the translational workforce. *J Clin Transl Sci*. 2020;4(4):286-293. doi:10.1017/cts.2020.2
12. Gonzales S, O'Keefe L, Gutzman K, et al. Translational Personas and Hospital Library Services. *J Hosp Librariansh*. 2020;20(3):204-216. doi:10.1080/15323269.2020.1778983
13. Gonzales S, Champieux R, Contaxis N, et al. Clinical and Translational Science Personas: Expansion and use cases. *J Clin Transl Sci*. 2023;7(1):e147. doi:10.1017/cts.2023.572
14. Clinical and Translational Science Personas. Clinical and Translational Science Personas. Published 2023. Accessed July 31, 2024. <https://zenodo.org/communities/cts-personas/>
15. Hunt JD, Whipple EC, McGowan JJ. Use of social network analysis tools to validate a resources infrastructure for interinstitutional translational research: a case study. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA*. 2012;100(1):48-54. doi:10.3163/1536-5050.100.1.009
16. Lackey MJ, Greenberg H, Rethlefsen ML. Building the Systematic Review Core in an academic health sciences library. *J Med Libr Assoc*. 2019;107(4):588-594. doi:10.5195/jmla.2019.711
17. Surkis A, Hogle JA, DiazGranados D, et al. Classifying publications from the clinical and translational science award program along the translational research spectrum: a machine learning approach. *J Transl Med*. 2016;14(1):235. doi:10.1186/s12967-016-0992-8
18. Fort DG, Herr TM, Shaw PL, Gutzman KE, Starren JB. Mapping the evolving definitions of translational research. *J Clin Transl Sci*. 2017;1(1):60-66. doi:10.1017/cts.2016.10
19. Sarli CC, Dubinsky EK, Holmes KL. Beyond citation analysis: a model for assessment of research impact. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA*. 2010;98(1):17-23. doi:10.3163/1536-5050.98.1.008
20. Luke DA, Sarli CC, Suiter AM, et al. The Translational Science Benefits Model: A New Framework for Assessing the Health and Societal Benefits of Clinical and Translational Sciences. *Clin Transl Sci*. 2018;11(1):77-84. doi:10.1111/cts.12495
21. Carpenter CR, Sarli CC, Fowler SA, et al. Best Evidence in Emergency Medicine (BEEM) rater scores correlate with publications' future citations. *Acad Emerg Med Off J Soc Acad Emerg Med*. 2013;20(10):1004-1012. doi:10.1111/acem.12235

22. Sarli CC, Carpenter CR. Measuring academic productivity and changing definitions of scientific impact. *Mo Med*. 2014;111(5):399-403.
23. Carpenter CR, Cone DC, Sarli CC. Using publication metrics to highlight academic productivity and research impact. *Acad Emerg Med Off J Soc Acad Emerg Med*. 2014;21(10):1160-1172. doi:10.1111/acem.12482
24. Champieux R, Coates H, Konkiel S, Gutzman K. Metrics Toolkit: an online evidence-based resource for navigating the research metrics landscape. *J Med Libr Assoc*. 2018;106(4):496-497. doi:10.5195/jmla.2018.526
25. Gutzman KE, Bales ME, Belter CW, et al. Research evaluation support services in biomedical libraries. *J Med Libr Assoc*. 2018;106(1):1-14. doi:10.5195/jmla.2018.205
26. Holmes KL, Lyon JA, Johnson LM, Sarli CC, Tennant MR. Library-based clinical and translational research support. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA*. 2013;101(4):326-335. doi:10.3163/1536-5050.101.4.017
27. Bakker C, Chew K. Evaluative Bibliometrics Meets the Clinical and Translational Science Institute. In: ; 2016. Accessed May 28, 2024. <https://www.mlanet.org/d/do/6882>
28. Gutzman KE, Holmes KL. Research Impact and Evaluation Services in the Library: One Piece at a Time. In: ; 2016. Accessed May 28, 2024. <https://www.mlanet.org/d/do/6880>; <https://jmla.pitt.edu/ojs/jmla/article/view/123/1466&sa=D&source=docs&ust=172255549174832&usg=AOvVaw1BZJisYI7wIU6N-v5to4U6>
29. Gutzman KE, Shaw PL, Mohammadi E, Holmes KL. The Mosaic of Translation: An Analysis of Translational Medicine Publications. In: ; 2016. Accessed May 28, 2024. <https://www.mlanet.org/d/do/6880>; <https://jmla.pitt.edu/ojs/jmla/article/view/123/1466&sa=D&source=docs&ust=172255549174832&usg=AOvVaw1BZJisYI7wIU6N-v5to4U6>
30. Yu F, Van AA, Patel T, et al. Bibliometrics approach to evaluating the research impact of CTSA: A pilot study. *J Clin Transl Sci*. 2020;4(4):336-344. doi:10.1017/cts.2020.29
31. Yu F, Patel T, Carnegie A, Dave G. Evaluating the impact of a CTSA program from 2008 to 2021 through bibliometrics, social network analysis, and altmetrics. *J Clin Transl Sci*. 2023;7(1):e44. doi:10.1017/cts.2022.530
32. Cleveland AD, Holmes KL, Philbrick JL. "Genomics and Translational Medicine for Information Professionals": an innovative course to educate the next generation of librarians. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA*. 2012;100(4):303-305. doi:10.3163/1536-5050.100.4.013
33. Loudon D. Clinical Research Scholars as a Microcosm for Exploring Effective Library Support for the Translational Research Community. Presented at: Medical Library Association 2014; May 19, 2014; Chicago, Illinois. <https://www.mlanet.org/d/do/23072>

34. Meyer S, Schaefer N. Librarians Collaboration with Clinical Translational Science Institute (CTSI) to Create Informatics Tools to Support Precision Health Research. Presented at: Medical Library Association 2020; July 24, 2020; Virtual. <https://www.mlanet.org/d/do/18121>
35. Gonzales S, Champieux R, Contaxis N, et al. Clinical and Translational Science Personas: Expansion and use cases. *J Clin Transl Sci.* 2023;7(1):e147. doi:10.1017/cts.2023.572
36. iTHRIV. Accessed July 31, 2024. <https://portal.ithriv.org/#/home>
37. Denton A. HSL: NIH Data Management and Sharing Plan Guidance: Overview. Accessed July 31, 2024. <https://guides.hsl.virginia.edu/nih-dmsp/overview>
38. Ragon B. HSL: Team Science Learning Module: Team Science Module Home. Accessed August 1, 2024. <https://guides.hsl.virginia.edu/c.php?g=1205269&p=8814790>
39. Albert PJ, Joshi A. Dynamically generating T32 training documents using structured data. *J Med Libr Assoc.* 2019;107(3). doi:10.5195/jmla.2019.401
40. AI in Healthcare: A guide introducing artificial intelligence as it applies to healthcare. Published online July 5, 2024. Accessed July 23, 2024. <https://hslguides.med.nyu.edu/aihsl/>
41. Conducting research through an anti-racism lens. Published online February 28, 2024. Accessed July 23, 2024. <https://libguides.umn.edu/antiracism/lens>
42. Claude Moore Health Sciences Library. HSL: IDEA Resources: Home. Accessed October 21, 2022. <https://guides.hsl.virginia.edu/c.php?g=1189620&p=8700724>
43. Read K, LaPolla FWZ. A new hat for librarians: providing REDCap support to establish the library as a central data hub. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA.* 2018;106(1):120-126. doi:10.5195/jmla.2018.327
44. Lauseng DL, Alpi KM, Linares BM, Sullo E, von Isenburg M. Library involvement in health informatics education for health professions students and practitioners: a scoping review. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA.* 2021;109(3):365-375. doi:10.5195/jmla.2021.1081
45. Federer L. Defining data librarianship: a survey of competencies, skills, and training. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA.* 2018;106(3):294-303. doi:10.5195/jmla.2018.306
46. Pinfield S, Cox AM, Smith J. Research Data Management and Libraries: Relationships, Activities, Drivers and Influences. Launois P, ed. *PLoS ONE.* 2014;9(12):e114734. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0114734
47. LaPolla FWZ, Bakker CJ, Exner N, Montnech T, Surkis A, Ye H. Rigor and reproducibility instruction in academic medical libraries. *J Med Libr Assoc.* 2022;110(3):281-293. doi:10.5195/jmla.2022.1443
48. Oxley PR, Ruffing J, Campion TR, Wheeler TR, Cole CL. Design and Implementation of a Secure Computing Environment for Analysis of Sensitive Data at an Academic Medical Center. *AMIA Annu Symp Proc AMIA Symp.* 2018;2018:857-866.

49. Wheeler TR, Oxley PR. Developing a Library Bioinformatics Program Fully Integrated into a Medical Research Institution. *Med Ref Serv Q*. 2018;37(4):413-421. doi:10.1080/02763869.2018.1514915
50. Johnson SB, Bales ME, Dine D, Bakken S, Albert PJ, Weng C. Automatic generation of investigator bibliographies for institutional research networking systems. *J Biomed Inform*. 2014;51:8-14. doi:10.1016/j.jbi.2014.03.013
51. ReCiter: An open source, identity-driven, authorship prediction algorithm optimized for academic institutions | PLOS ONE. Accessed August 1, 2024. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0244641>
52. Santangelo G. iCite Database Snapshots (NIH Open Citation Collection). Published online July 16, 2024. doi:10.35092/yhjc.c.4586573
53. GitHub - wcmc-its/ReCiter-Publication-Manager: ReCiter Publication Manager - a user interface for providing feedback on articles. Accessed July 29, 2024. <https://github.com/wcmc-its/reciter-publication-manager>
54. Sheridan H, Dellureficio AJ, Ratajeski MA, Mannheimer S, Wheeler TR. Data Curation through Catalogs: A Repository-Independent Model for Data Discovery. *J EScience Librariansh*. 2021;10(3):1203. doi:10.7191/jeslib.2021.1203
55. Yee M, Surkis A, Lamb I, Contaxis N. The NYU Data Catalog: a modular, flexible infrastructure for data discovery. *J Am Med Inform Assoc JAMIA*. 2023;30(10):1693-1700. doi:10.1093/jamia/ocad125
56. U.S. Repository Network. SPARC. Accessed July 31, 2024. <https://sparcopen.org/our-work/us-repository-network/>
57. Fay B, Buda LM, Dellureficio AJ, et al. The Medical Institutional Repositories in Libraries (MIRL) Symposium: a blueprint designed in response to a community of practice need. *J Med Libr Assoc*. 2023;111(3):710-716. doi:10.5195/jmla.2023.1503
58. Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI). Accessed July 31, 2024. <https://datascience.nih.gov/data-ecosystem/generalist-repository-ecosystem-initiative>
59. Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative | Data Science at NIH. Accessed July 31, 2024. <https://datascience.nih.gov/data-ecosystem/generalist-repository-ecosystem-initiative>
60. Johnson SB, Bales ME, Dine D, Bakken S, Albert PJ, Weng C. Automatic generation of investigator bibliographies for institutional research networking systems. *J Biomed Inform*. 2014;51:8-14. doi:10.1016/j.jbi.2014.03.013

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- ⁴ Indiana University School of Medicine, Ruth Lilly Medical Library
 - ⁵ Indiana Clinical & Translational Sciences Institute
 - ⁶ Johns Hopkins University, Welch Medical Library
 - ⁷ Health Sciences Library, NYU Grossman School of Medicine
 - ⁸ East Carolina University, Laupus Health Sciences Library
 - ⁹ University of Washington
 - ¹⁰ Health Sciences Library & Informatics Center, University of New Mexico
 - ¹¹ University of Minnesota
 - ¹² University of Alabama at Birmingham
 - ¹³ University of Central Florida Health Science Library College of Medicine
 - ¹⁴ University of Pittsburgh
 - ¹⁵ NYU Langone Health, NYU Health Sciences Library
 - ¹⁶ University of Nebraska Medical Center
 - ¹⁷ University of Mississippi Medical Center
 - ¹⁸ Queen's University
 - ¹⁹ University of California, San Francisco
 - ²⁰ Tulane University
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 - ²² University of Illinois Chicago, Library of Health Sciences
 - ²³ Duke University Medical Center Library
 - ²⁴ University of Chicago
 - ²⁵ Weill Cornell Medicine
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